

“Fighting for Survival”: How Representative Assemblies Survived Early Modern European State Formation

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In the Early Modern Period, transaction costs declined as a result of improvements in literacy, numeracy and infrastructure. At the same time, military developments in gunpowder, technology and infantry tactics created an additional advantage for larger, centralised organisations. Together, these changes undermined the feudal system of power-sharing between central rulers and their vassal nobility for which representative assemblies had been designed. No longer required to collect taxes on behalf of the ruler or able to threaten rebellion, the nobility and their parliaments lost their original function. Still, many parliaments survived, leading scholars to propose several long-term causes, often dating back to the early Middle Ages (Ertman, 1997; Graves, 2011; D’Arcy & Nistotskaya, 2018). This paper challenges such theories by proposing a different mechanism, drawing on primary sources as well as a range of secondary literature. Focusing on three prominent case studies of armed conflict between parliamentary interests and the sovereign – the English Civil War and the Glorious Revolution, the French Fronde and the Dutch Revolt – it argues that while central rulers gained a structural advantage in the Early Modern Period, parliaments could prevail through success in military conflict. This required the confluence of several factors: (1) succession crises that weakened dynastic stability and legitimacy, (2) broad social alliances across different groups against the central ruler, and (3) foreign intervention in support of parliamentary interests.

INTRODUCTION

As power-sharing mechanisms between local potentates, central rulers and other interest groups, representative assemblies organised tax collection and facilitated the political rights of an armed nobility in the feudal polity. Their evolution over time, their relative strength in different political systems, and their effect on economic development have been debated extensively (Ertman, 1997; Stasavage, 2010; Van Zanden et al., 2012; Blaydes and Chaney, 2013). In the Early Modern Period, states formed as central political organisations that monopolised the legitimate supply of violence, fundamentally changing medieval power relations. Using a range of primary and secondary sources, this paper sets out to explore the impact of this process on representative assemblies – a relationship existing scholarship has not yet investigated comprehensively.

The same developments that facilitated state formation in Early Modern Europe also weakened and changed the role of representative assemblies. These were, namely, decreasing transaction costs, meaning “costs connected with the creation, use, or change of institutions or organizations,” and changes in military tactics and technology (Volckart, 2000, p. 3). Governing large territories became cheaper, and military developments made it easier for central rulers – sovereign monarchs ruling over a nobility in charge of vassal principalities – to dominate their vassals. As monarchs across most of Europe worked to construct absolutist states at the expense of representative assemblies, tensions between monarchical and parliamentary interests arose, often culminating in military conflict (Cuttica & Burgess, 2012, p. 4). What follows will show that developments occurring immediately before or during these conflicts – hereinafter referred to as “proximate factors” – determined their outcome and, as a result, the long-term survival of representative assemblies. This challenges a strand of existing literature, which argues that medieval conditions or fundamental economic and political structures determined the strength of parliaments over the long run, adding to the broader debate on institutional persistence (Ertman, 1997; Graves, 2011; D’Arcy and Nistotskaya, 2018).

In the first section, “The End of Bargaining,” this paper argues that representative assemblies are the outcome of negotiations between the monarch and other interest groups to perform state functions, primarily taxation and protection. This was necessary for effective government in an environment

where rule through a central body alone was impossible due to high transaction costs and powerful local interests. As transaction costs decreased and military tactics and technology increasingly favoured larger centralised organisations in the Early Modern Period, central rulers no longer needed parliaments to raise taxes or protect their realm, pitting them against each other in a competition for centralised control (Volckart, 2000). The section “Equally Absolutist Tendencies” then shows that this new environment created similar tensions between parliamentary and monarchical interests in different European polities. The final section, “Surviving State Formation,” discusses the three most prominent case studies of Early Modern conflict between parliaments and central rulers: The English Civil War and the Glorious Revolution, the French Fronde and the Dutch Revolt. Each case is discussed to illustrate the following argument: Although developments in military tactics and technology and falling transaction costs afforded central rulers an innate advantage, parliaments could survive if three factors aligned to increase their relative power in a military conflict. (1) succession crises weakening the legitimacy and political stability of the central dynasty, (2) broad social alliances across different interest groups forming against the central ruler, and (3) foreign intervention in support of parliamentary interests.

THE END OF BARGAINING

Across medieval Europe, feudal rule was negotiated between local elites and the monarch. Under typical feudal conditions, as outlined by North (1990), central rulers lacked the capacity to collect taxes across their territory and the military power to respond to threats of rebellion by their local nobility. They were forced to bargain with their vassals, offering political rights in exchange for the collection of taxes on their behalf, the supply of military forces, and recognition as overlord (North, 1990; Boix et al., 2013; Boucoyannis, 2015). The Treaty of Thübingen is a case in point (Sander and Spangenberg, 1965). The “body of subjects” referring to the principalities and religious institutions represented in this “parliament” agreed to pay a certain sum each year, as well as the interest incurred by the ruler for loans he had previously taken out to fund a military campaign. In return, the parliament received several substantial rights, such as the right to “consent” to any “campaigns he (the duke) may undertake in the future,” any mortgage on “land, people, castles, towns, and villages,” and taxes (Sander and Spangenberg, 1965). Similarly, out of financial pressure and to appease rebellious barons, King John of England granted significant rights to a council of 25 of his barons in the Magna Carta. Similarly, out of financial pressure and to appease rebellious nobles, King John of England granted significant rights to a council of 25 of his barons in the Magna Carta. No general “aid or scutage” (taxes) was to be levied in England without the council’s consent (Holt, 2015). In both cases, the representative assembly received substantial political power from bargaining between the central ruler and his vassals for political rights and resources. In the case of Thübingen, the nobles represented were tasked with locally sourcing revenues to support a military campaign, whereas the Magna Carta was, to a certain extent, the result of an armed rebellion by English barons against King John and their reluctance to support his taxation policies. These cases suggest that the representative assembly had two key *raison d’être*: the need for and inability of the central ruler to raise sufficient resources for military campaigns or other activities, and the desire of armed nobles, who were able to “credibly threaten a rebellion” to achieve political rights (Te Brake, p. 157).

States formed as a set of historical developments caused a decrease in transaction costs, enabling central organisations to effectively supply protection to and tax populations. This removed the first *raison d’être* of parliaments: the need to raise sufficient revenues. As contractual views on state formation show, medieval levels of transaction costs were too high for transactions involving entire political organisations to take place (Volckart, 2000, p. 272). Low literacy rates meant that the drafting of contracts was difficult, the limited use of currency created high costs for raising taxes, and bad infrastructure made communication between the centre and faraway regions difficult (Volckart, 2000, p. 272). Parliaments granted political rights to the local nobility, who in turn raised taxes on behalf of the central ruler in their principalities. In the Early Modern Period, conditions changed, allowing states to centralise control. Literacy rates increased substantially in Western Europe during the Early Modern Period. Using book and manuscript production, Buringh and Van Zanden (2009, p. 434) calculate an increase from 12 percent literacy in the period 1421-1500 to 31 percent in 1700-1800. The influx of New World Bullion facilitated Early Modern European monetary expansion, further reducing transaction costs. Palma’s GDP deflated coin stock index illustrates this expansion for England, doubling in the period 1550-1790 (Battilossi et al., 2020, p. 14). The development for other European countries was similar (Battilossi et al., 2020, p. 14). The third crucial development was the reduction in transport costs. In the late twelfth century, messengers in Central Europe, for example, could cover

daily distances of roughly 40 miles travelling by horse. At the beginning of the 16th century, this distance increased, reaching 60 miles in some records (Volckart, 2000, p. 274). These Early Modern reductions in transaction costs made it easier for the centre to break free of its reliance on the local nobility for tax revenue. As transaction costs declined, collecting taxes themselves, independent of the local nobility, became increasingly attractive to central rulers. After a threshold in the development of transaction costs was reached, parliaments, as facilitators of power-sharing with the nobility, would become redundant in the eyes of the central ruler, turning them into a competitor for central state functions rather than a necessary partner.

The second *raison d'être* was weakened by military developments, which reduced the power of noble threats to central rule and worked towards the monopolisation of violence by the monarch. Hoffman (2015) shows that a “tournament mechanism” – working through military competition between equally powerful European states – led to innovations in gunpowder technology and the re-emergence of organised infantry units under centralised control. Both developments favoured the central ruler’s power (Hoffman, 2015, p. 40). The improved effectiveness of gunpowder weapons reduced the defensive capabilities of castle walls and increased the vulnerability of the local nobility to potential military campaigns from the centre (Bean, 1973, p. 207). In the late fifteenth century, Charles VII of France was able to raze 60 fortified locations in only 369 days using gunpowder weapons efficiently. He completed his campaign in a fraction of the time it took the British for their invasion of the same castles before the widespread use of gunpowder (Hoffman, 2015, p. 39). The share of mounted knights in combat – mostly supplied by local nobility – also declined significantly starting in the 1600s, as organised infantry proved to be more effective (Storrs and Scott, 1996, p. 1). Systems of feudal levies were thus replaced by a tax to be paid by the nobility, first in Spain in 1631, followed by Britain and France (Storrs and Scott, 1996, p. 5). The organisational capacity required to maintain a large organised infantry and the resource intensity of gunpowder weapons, coupled with the relative weakening of castle walls, favoured central rulers militarily vis-à-vis local nobility. These new methods of warfare also reduced the ruler’s reliance on nobles, who were not required to fight as knights anymore.

The armed nobility became increasingly redundant as central rulers could monopolise the supply of protection. Parliament lost its role as a facilitator of political rights for an armed nobility. In fully formed states, the central government, as the monopoly, could enforce the extraction of taxes from the population within its territory. Local potentates no longer posed serious threats to the centre’s power. Instead, government became a set of centralised functions without the need for a feudal “division of labour” between local nobility and central ruler. The monarch and parliaments became competitors for these functions, with the central monarch in a much stronger military position.

EQUALLY ABSOLUTIST TENDENCIES

Yet parliaments survived in England, the Netherlands, Poland, and elsewhere. The Early Modern Period brought about constitutional monarchies with powerful legislative assemblies. Scholars have accounted for this with deep historical drivers which differentiated certain polities from others (Graves, 2011; Ertman, 1997). Comparing the level of executive constraint in England and France shows that these systems were more similar than assumed by such scholarship, at least until the decisive events of the Fronde and the Glorious Revolution. Ertman (1997) argues that the survival of parliaments through the Early Modern Period was a result of deep processes beginning in the Middle Ages. Failed medieval state-making created fractured political landscapes and powerful elites in Latin Europe. Rulers had to send officials from the centre to provinces to reassert royal prerogatives, distributing privileges to select groups and creating non-participatory institutions. According to Ertman (1998), the English Kingdom, in contrast, was built on “virgin territory, unencumbered by the legacy of unsuccessful dark age state building” (Ertman, 1997, p. 157). Its representative system was able to form on a geographical basis, and local government built participatory communities. The British system was put on a fundamentally different, more participatory, trajectory of state formation, so the argument goes (Ertman, 1997).

Yet, the political circumstances in France and Britain were more alike than Ertman’s theory on the lasting effect of medieval conditions suggests. In fact, the English monarchs often wielded even more executive power than their French counterparts. This was the case despite their contrasting institutional heritage as outlined by Ertman (1997). French absolutist monarchs in the sixteenth and early seventeenth centuries struggled to remove judges and local officials or to influence court proceedings to affect death sentences. At the same time, in England, the Stuarts and Tudors wielded

significant powers over the judiciary (Henshall, 1992, p. 28). They could intervene in court proceedings and use an emergency prerogative, which allowed them to sentence anyone who was found guilty by their Privy Council to prison (Henshall, 1992, p. 27). The excessive exploitation of this power by the English Monarch was mentioned explicitly at the beginning of the Petition of Right of 1628 (Frohnen, 2002). By the early 17th century, English monarchs also reserved the right to impose martial law in peacetime and raise significant taxes through “forced loans” (Frohnen, 2002). When Charles I encountered resistance to his imposition of these forced loans, he threatened to “sweep the benches” of parliament (Prest, 1988, p. 175). While the French monarch had more legislative rights, the English kings were able to intervene significantly in judicial proceedings and matters of taxation (Miller, 1964, p. 188). Before their respective revolutions, the two systems were more similar in terms of the extent of unchecked power the monarch could wield than theories of persistent trajectories of participatory versus non-participatory state formation would suggest.

Similarly, a comparison of Britain and France challenges existing theories connecting the economic and political structure and shape of a polity to the strength of parliaments. In one example of such a perspective, Graves argues that bicameral systems could have been a factor in the evolution of stronger parliaments because aristocratic and clerical interests were counterbalanced by an equally strong chamber representing the “commons” (Graves, 2001, p. 163). Others have pointed to urbanisation as an obstacle in the formation of large coercive states, fostering stronger representative assemblies (D’Arcy and Nistotskaya, 2018). Scholarship has also argued that, where there were powerful commercial activities, merchants were able to secure their interests in parliament, contributing to a favourable growth environment, which in turn led to commercial activity (Acemoglu et al., 2005). England checks all the above conditions. It had a bicameral system consisting of a House of Commons and a House of Lords and its economy was exceptionally developed and urbanised by the 17th century by European standards. Allen’s data shows that England’s non-agricultural population made up a higher share than Latin Europe’s starting in 1500 and continuing throughout the Early Modern Period. (Allen, 2003, p. 408). However, the type of representation in the English parliament is not consistent with the theories outlined above. In 1710, a Landed Qualifications Bill was approved in the House of Commons, which included a requirement for a minimum income of at least 600 pounds from land to qualify as a “knight of the shire” in the House of Commons, with some exceptions for heirs (Clark, 2010). The Bill’s enforcement did not lead to many expulsions, showing that even after the Glorious Revolution, the House of Commons was dominated by the landed elite (Hayton, 2002). Between 1660 and 1685 the percentage of Members of Parliament classified as merchants fluctuated between a low point of 7 percent in 1661 to high point of 11 percent in 1679 – far from any relative majority and significantly less than the representation for “country gentlemen” which made up over 50 percent for the entire period reaching 61 percent in 1681 (Hayton, 2002). Throughout the Early Modern period, the English Parliament was dominated by the landed country gentry, similar to the parlements and local assemblies in France, or the Cortes in Spain. High levels of urbanisation, commercial activities and bicameralism do not necessarily lead to merchant-dominated parliaments, calling into question the link between the structure of the economy, the type of parliament and its likelihood of survival.

Parliamentary activity data shows that the English parliament before the Glorious Revolution was not significantly more powerful or active than many Latin European parliaments. By 1640, there had been eleven years of rule without parliament in England, and parliamentary activity throughout much of the fifteenth, sixteenth and late seventeenth centuries – as measured in sessions convened and laws passed – was lower than during the fourteenth century (Tilly, 1995; Van Zanden et al., 2012). Before the Glorious Revolution, the English monarchy successfully set up several non-participatory institutions similar to those which were widespread across much of Latin Europe, limiting parliamentary activity and influence over significant periods of time. French assemblies, on the other hand, were more vibrant than often assumed. They had rural elections, and the Third Estate engaged in several efforts to increase voter participation during the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries (Graves, 2001, p. 175). The lack of executive constraint, the structure of the English parliament with a high representation of landed gentry, and the low level of parliamentary activity before the Glorious Revolution challenge the argument that Early Modern European political systems differed fundamentally as a result of deep historical drivers. Evidence from France and Britain suggests that the two systems were remarkably similar. As central rulers gained power vis-à-vis local nobility and other interests, powerful monarchies were set up across the continent.

SURVIVING STATE FORMATION

Many civil conflicts of the long seventeenth century can be seen as battles for the survival of parliament. Most prominently, the English Civil War culminating in the Glorious Revolution, the Fronde in France and the Dutch Revolt, were motivated by a desire to protect political rights against the power of an increasingly absolutist monarch. A key document highlighting the ongoing struggle between the English Parliament and the monarchy in the lead-up to the civil war was the Petition of Rights drafted by the House of Commons and addressed to Charles I. It set out key demands: “that no man be compelled to yield any tax without commons consent by act of Parliament” and “no man shall be forejudged of life or limb against the law of the land” (Frohnen, 2002). Similarly, the French Fronde was motivated by anti-absolutist sentiments, as the countless “Marazinades” (polemic texts against royalist Cardinal Marazin) show. One of the chief polemicists for Condés party – the group fighting the monarchy – wrote in one of his 50 pamphlets: “It is not to be doubted that kings would have wishes contrary to the good of the state, if kings had wishes contrary to those of the princes, parlements and people” (Du Bosc de Montandré, 1652). This shows that the movement pushed for a limit to royal prerogative power and viewed parliamentary and princely interests as more legitimate. The open and explicit negation of the absolute principle of rule without consent by other interest groups is further testament to the anti-absolutist nature of the movement. The powerful and dynamic deliberative assemblies that evolved as part of the Ormée – a local manifestation of the Fronde in Bordeaux – illustrate what could have been the outcome had the Fronde been militarily successful (Scott, 1995, p. 935). The Dutch Revolution was also driven by the right to ensure parliamentary privileges as the Act of Abjuration shows. It declared the goal of securing “ancient liberties and privileges” that had been lost as a result of the “enslavement” by the Habsburgs (Dutch Act of Abjuration, 1581). These documents were drafted either in the lead-up to or during civil wars between the monarch and other interest groups. They show that these civil conflicts were characterised by the desire of interests represented in parliament to restore rights that had been threatened or entirely revoked by a monarch gradually extending their powers.

Despite the central ruler’s significant military advantage, the Glorious Revolution, the Fronde and the Dutch Revolt were decisive points in the long-run development of representative assemblies. Proximate factors could significantly weaken and threaten the ruler. Both the English Glorious Revolution and the French Fronde occurred in times of succession crises, which weakened central authority. In 1655, Colonel John Penruddock sought to place Charles II’s illegitimate but Protestant son in line of the crown ahead of Catholic James (Tilly, 1995, p. 124). The French Fronde occurred after the simultaneous deaths of Louis XIII and his powerful minister Cardinal Richelieu in 1643, during the regency of Anne of Austria, the mother of Louis XIV, who was still a child (Te Brake, 1998, p. 151). Kokkonen and Moller (2020) have already argued that succession crises can lead to short-term concessions to parliament. What follows will go further and show that, together with broad social alliances and foreign intervention, succession crises can strengthen parliamentary interest enough to create decisive moments in the long-term institutional development of states.

By forming alliances across societal strata, counter-absolutist movements were able to pose a significant and long-term challenge to the ruler. Charles’s view of top-down reformation rallied a coalition of “parliamentarians, Presbyterians and independents” against him in the early 1630s, while London’s merchants worked with the invading and revolutionary forces (Tilly, 1995; Te Brake, 1998). In the French Fronde, Parliamentarians (members of local courts), local nobility and ordinary people entered an alliance that was able to credibly threaten royal rule (Te Brake, 1998). The Dutch Revolt was able to form strong and persistent pockets of resistance by creating alliances between local merchants and nobility, while common people rioted, often breaking into catholic churches, and destroying sacred images (Tilly, 1995). In all three uprisings, the nobility had the support of ordinary people, guilds and merchants. This added to weaknesses in the centre, caused by succession crises and explains why parliamentary interests could pose a significant challenge to the central ruler.

Foreign intervention was crucial in ensuring that parliaments were able to soundly defeat monarchical interests, establishing new institutions over the long run. The Glorious Revolution relied on an invasion of England by Dutch troops, deposing the ruling monarch and installing a constitutional monarchy with the help of local merchants and some of the nobility (Tilly, 1995, p. 124). The Fronde did not receive this kind of foreign support. The Ormée in Bordeaux attempted to use the city’s strong trading links with Britain to ask Cromwell for support but was rejected (Scott, 1995, p. 935). When the

parliament took over Paris in 1649 and, gaining wide support there, it forced the King, his mother and their advisors to flee, but only achieved short-term concessions. (Te Brake, 1998, p. 152). Condé's armies were eventually defeated in 1653, after which rebels across the country surrendered (Kokkonen and Møller 2020, p. 954). The outcome was the construction of an exceptionally absolutist state. Still, the Fronde should be seen as a significant challenge to absolutism. Had it been successful, potentially through help from Britain, the vibrant local parliaments provide a glimpse of the French system that could have been (Belk, 1985). Similarly, the Dutch case fits neatly into this framework. While there were no English "boots on the ground" in the Netherlands, English forces fought Spain throughout the period, diverting significant forces away from the war effort (Tilly, 1995, p. 63). Spain was also at war with France at the same time (Tilly, 1995, p. 63). This allowed Maurice of Nassau to force a truce on the thinly stretched Spanish army and achieve de facto independence in 1609. The system that followed had a strong parliament and limited the executive power of the monarch. The examples of the Glorious Revolution, the Fronde and the Dutch Revolt show that proximate factors impacting the outcomes of military conflicts between parliamentary interests and the monarch should be seen as decisive moments for the long-term development of representative assemblies. All three polities started out with monarchical dynasties seeking to set up absolutist systems. In the long seventeenth century, parliamentary interests organised in armed rebellions to defend their privileges. Exploiting weaknesses in the centre, forming cross-societal alliances, and using foreign support, they were able to pose a significant challenge to the monarch and, in the cases of the Dutch Provinces and England, create constitutional monarchies that lasted for centuries to come.

CONCLUSION

The strength of representative assemblies was inextricably linked to feudal conditions throughout Europe. Once conditions changed, reducing the cost of governing larger territories and increasing the relative military power of the central authority, parliaments had to fight for survival. Transaction costs declined, reducing the centre's dependence on local powerholders for taxes, and developments in military tactics and technology reduced the ability of nobles to threaten rebellion. The central ruler could use their military advantage to monopolise the market for protection and threaten the political rights of the nobility represented in parliament. This tension between a monopolising monarch and the desire of local nobility to retain their parliamentary powers led to civil war in many locations during the Long 17th Century. Analysing the cases of the English Civil War and Glorious Revolution, the French Fronde and the Dutch Revolt, this paper shows that parliamentary interests could exploit moments of weakness in the centre, ally with other social groups, and, with foreign support, pose a serious challenge to the central ruler. In England and the Netherlands, victorious parliamentary forces could then establish lasting constitutional monarchies with powerful representative assemblies. This paper challenges existing literature on deep historical drivers that shaped the survival of representative assemblies. Demonstrating the power of proximate factors and armed conflict, it cautions against determinism in explaining the persistence of political institutions. Further research into the developments and armed conflicts discussed here and additional case studies of Early Modern struggle between parliaments, local interests and central rulers could add to the broader debate on the forces that determined the shape and structure of states.

Arthur Kroen

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